

Our Proposed Solution

Our proposal to fill this gap is to develop a modular, accessible, and simple web-based platform for survey planning and quality assurance, with a “front end” that has a non-threatening, question-and-answer format and avoids a programming-like structure or display of off-putting equations.

The aim of the Survey Planning, Allocation, Costing and Evaluation (SPACE) Project is to create this online platform whose interacting modules will:

- Help budget resources effectively (Costing module)
- Assist decision-making about the spacing of transects, cores, or shovel tests (Sweep Width module)
- Define strata and allocate effort optimally in disproportionate stratified cluster samples (Allocation module)
- Determine adequate sample sizes (Sample Size module)
- Allocate effort in surveys guided by predictive models (Allocation module)
- Provide more empirical estimates of visibility (Visibility module)
- And estimate survey coverage as a quality indicator (Coverage module)

To accomplish these goals, we need to identify the decisions that survey planners must make and the information inputs they need to make these decisions. For example, a Flow Diagram for some of the decisions, inputs and outputs involved in designing a stratified cluster sample for a fieldwalking survey (fig. 1) has inputs from a GIS and a budget, an allocation process that may be proportionate or disproportionate and, for disproportionate sampling, options to minimize

relative error on estimates of key parameters or to minimize cost for a fixed, acceptable error. It also includes a process for post-survey testing the strata to ensure that they have been effective at partitioning variability in the population.

Applications, or “Why do This?”

We hope that the SPACE modules will assist archaeologists in a number of ways. For those conducting academic surveys, they will help them achieve objectives within their typically restrictive budgets and allow greater confidence in survey results.

In the heritage industry, we would expect the Sweep Width and related modules to be especially useful for surveys that “clear” a space for development by allowing greater confidence that they have not missed significant cultural resources. Once development has begun, it can be extremely costly to mitigate unanticipated sites that surveys failed to detect (Campana 2017:4; Schiffer 1987:353).

Fig. 1. Flow chart for designing a stratified cluster sample for a fieldwalking survey. It has inputs from a GIS and a budget, an allocation process that may be proportionate or disproportionate and, for disproportionate sampling, options to minimize relative error on estimates of key parameters or to minimize cost for a fixed, acceptable error.

Fig. 2. Flow chart for an archaeological survey by fieldwalking that employs a predictive model and optimal allocation. The allocation requires inputs from experts or empirical data, or both, data from the GIS model on the sizes of spaces and coverage to date, information on resources available, and updated information on field conditions and site or artifact detections as survey progresses. The design and implementation is too complex to be easily accomplished “on the fly,” but most of the processes are relatively easy to automate.

In another example (fig. 2), the Flow Diagram for allocating survey effort guided by a predictive model has processes based on classical Bayesian search allocation (Banning 2002; Koopman 1980; Stone 1975). This tool, originally developed to search for U-boats during the Second World War, has been the basis of search-and-rescue for decades, but has rarely seen use in archaeology (Hitchings et al. 2016). Archaeologists’ failure to take note of this method may be due to the inaccurate perception that it is too computationally complex. Automating the

mathematics, however, should make this useful method much more accessible to archaeologists.

The product we are developing includes several distinct modules, most of which are currently at the conceptual stage. In addition, most of these currently emphasize fieldwalking, but one is explicitly for subsurface survey. In this paper, we focus on the only module for which we have a working prototype, the Sweep Width module.

Sweep-Width Module

The purpose of this module is to help survey planners estimate sweep widths for fieldwalking in varying conditions (Banning et al. 2011, 2017; Milwid 2016). Sweep width (W) is the most general summary of all the factors that contribute to the probability that surveyors will find targets, whether sites or artifacts, and concerns the relationship between range (the perpendicular distance from the surveyor's path to the target) and the probability that the surveyor will detect the target.

The data for the Sweep Width Module come from mock surveys, what we call "calibration runs," over fields that are ideally devoid of artifacts except for ones we have seeded in known locations at varying ranges from the surveyor's path. The reason for such mock surveys is that it is the only way of which we are aware to evaluate the actual effectiveness of survey teams at detecting artifacts. Resurvey, for example, is not sufficient for this because it is likely that both the original and the resurvey team missed some of them. The calibration field can be prepared with an actual grid marked by strings (Banning et al. 2007; 2011), but we have found that the artificiality of such a setup outweighs the greater precision of artifact placement that the strings allow. More recently, we have used invisible grids, marked only by a tape along the centre line and markers for major divisions, such as 25 m or 50 m to help surveyors track their progress along a walking transect (Banning et al. 2017). Surveyors scan the area left and right of the tape

as they walk, but have to estimate the range to each artifact they see to their left or right. They are not allowed to wander off the path to investigate it.

Each surveyor makes multiple calibration runs on a particular calibration field that has been selected as typical of some real survey conditions, and accumulates data on tablets, including time of day, a photo of the field, and the type and estimated range of artifacts to left or right of the path. We have used a custom data collection form in the Filemaker Go app, but other mobile data collection apps, such as ODK Collect, Qfield, or ArcGIS Collector¹, could equally fulfill this function. The digital data collection form also records surveyors' average speed from the tablets' built-in GPS. The full method for conducting calibration runs is explained in a supplementary document archived and accessible through Zenodo (Banning 2024). A direct permalink to this document is provided in the Materials and Methods section, below.

Once the calibration data are collected, they are uploaded to the Sweep Width module as .csv files. The module plots the reported detections by artifact type. Because surveyors vary in their estimates of distance, these plots show considerable spread in the range (fig. 3). To account for errors in estimating distances, the module currently uses a simplistic approach whereby an error tolerance is given to a hypothetical detection that is proportional to the estimated distance from the transect (we expect surveyors to estimate short distances more accurately than long ones). This tolerance represents the radius of a circle around the detection. If a seeded artifact is found to be within the error tolerance for a given estimate, it is deemed a positive detection. Future updates to the model will adapt more sophisticated approaches to accounting for errors in distance estimation, including algorithms based on psychology research on distance perception

¹ FileMaker Go <https://apps.apple.com/us/app/claris-filemaker-go-19/id1484857908>, ODK Collect https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=org.odk.collect.android&hl=en_CA&gl=US&pli=1, Qfield <https://qfield.org/>, ArcGIS <https://doc.arcgis.com/en/collector-classic/> (accessed 19 February 2024).

(Li et al. 2011; Loomis and Philbeck 2008; Ooi and He 2007) to create ellipses around the known locations of artifacts. Once the positive and negative detections (or “false positives”) have been counted, the module can use those data to display some general statistics, such as false-target rates, but the more important role of the positive detections is to calculate detection functions and sweep widths.

2. Locations of Suspected Detections

Fig. 3. View of the reported detections for a set of calibration runs on a field seeded with artifacts relevant to a forensic search (backpacks, fabric pieces, eyeglasses, shoes). Note the considerable spread in range, due to surveyors’ innaccurate estimates of distance.

Of the competing models for the relationship between detection probability and range away from the surveyor’s path (fig. 4), in our applications to both archaeological and forensic types of artifacts, we have found the exponential function most realistic. Sweep width (W) is the swath,

centered on the survey path, within which surveyors detect the same number of targets as they would have detected under the definite-detection model. Under definite detection,

Fig. 4. Three competing models for the relationship between detection probability (y-axis) and range from the transect centre-line: (a) definite detection, (b) inverse-cube detection, whereby detection probability declines with the cube of the range, and (c) exponential detection with sweep width (W), the grey area above the curve is equal to the grey area in the tails.

surveyors find 100% of targets within the sweep width and none at all outside it, which is not a realistic scenario. Under the exponential model, surveyors find just as many artifacts outside the sweep width as they fail to detect inside it, so these cancel out (the shaded areas in fig. 4c, fig. 5).

The Sweep Width Module uses the calibration data — either for single artifact types or for all of them combined — to calculate the detection probabilities for each artifact type at different ranges and then fits an exponential detection function:

$$p(r) = be^{-kr^2}$$

Here, $p(r)$ is the probability of detecting a target at range r , and b is the probability of detection right on the surveyor's path. The variable k in this function summarizes all the factors that contribute to detectability, including visibility in the field being surveyed, average surveyor speed, obtrusiveness and clustering of the target artifacts, and others. Sweep width is then just the area under the detection function; because probability is unitless, this area yields a result in meters.

Fig. 5. A visualization of sweep width in plan view. Note that the number of detected artifacts (red dots) outside W is equal to the number of undetected artifacts (white dots) within W (after Banning et al. 2011).

The value of k , and therefore of W , varies by artifact type, visibility and other aspects of field conditions. Determining it with calibration surveys allows us to account for these factors simultaneously. Ideally, such calibrations should occur regularly over the course of a survey and in calibration fields that vary in their characteristics but mimic the conditions in spaces that will be the subject of “real” survey.

Fig. 6. Example of some detection functions for lithic flakes (solid curves) and a variety of pottery (dashed curves) as determined from results on two different calibration fields, a pasture (a), and a plowed olive grove (b), in northern Jordan (after Banning et al. 2017).

We have tested this process on surveys in Jordan and Cyprus with mock surveys on field types that include olive groves, plowed fields, pastures, and harvested fields with stubble, and then applied the results to estimating coverages for actual surveys. In addition, we used sweep

widths estimated in this way, multiplied by the total amount of effort we would expect a survey team to make in a day (total meters walked) to allocate that effort near-optimally with Bayesian methods that we discuss elsewhere (fig. 6; Hitchings et al. 2016; Stewart et al. 2016). For example, in a region for which we estimated a sweep width of only 0.5 m, and an available effort of 5000 m, the coverage we would distribute among a set of survey spaces would be 2500 m². SPACE's Sweep Width Module automates the calculations once the calibration data are available, and we can update the estimates of Sweep Width as additional calibrations are complete.

Once sufficient data are available to provide sweep widths for the artifact types and conditions to be expected in a survey, we can use these to either provide a basis for selecting effective transect spacings or, after a more standard survey is complete, allow accurate estimates of the probability that the survey has missed "targets" of a given size and density. In Jordan and Cyprus, we used the resulting sweep widths to distribute survey effort with Bayesian allocation (Hitchings et al. 2016; Stewart et al. 2016).

Because k varies by artifact type, survey planners must decide which value they want to use for planning purposes. If they want to be conservative, and minimize the risk of missing targets, they might use the smallest sweep width among the ones the module calculates. If they want to be more cost-conscious, they might elect to use the sweep width for the most important artifact type even if it is relatively large, or an intermediary one for all artifact types combined. Whatever choice they make, SPACE would fully inform survey planners of the potential impacts of that choice in terms of the risk of missed detections or error in density estimates.

Ideally, projects would carry out their own calibrations to account for the specific conditions, including personnel, that are unique to those projects. However, we anticipate that some projects

experience barriers to doing this. Consequently, we hope to make an online version of SPACE available that would allow users to access sweep width data from other projects operating with similar conditions. This will require creating a large database of anonymized, open-access data that past users have made available for different combinations of terrain, vegetation, and artifact types. We recognize that archaeologists may be reluctant to conduct calibration surveys, whether for their own use or as contributions to such a database. However, the costs are not prohibitive. In our survey in Jordan, for example, we devoted only six calibration sessions, each about three hours long, in which surveyors in turns made multiple passes along the survey path. This provided sufficient data to yield sweep widths.

The results of the Sweep Width module provide critical inputs to some of the other modules, still under development. For example, coverage is just the product of sweep width and the total length of all survey transects, determined in a GIS, while dividing coverage by the total area of the survey region provides a basic summary of how thorough a survey has been. Sweep width is also a key consideration for allocating effort, whether that is simply deciding on transect spacings, allocating coverage to each stratum in a stratified sample, or estimating posterior probabilities that undiscovered sites remain in certain spaces in a predictive model. Even approximate estimates of sweep width allow surveyors to use transect spacings that assure a minimum coverage of surveyed spaces or, for surveys that follow fixed, regulated transect spacings, allow them to estimate artifact densities in survey patches or the probability, and therefore the risk, that the survey could have missed artifact scatters.

Our working prototype of the Sweep Width Module is written in the open-source scripting language R, and makes use of some common data-analysis packages (`dplyr`, `ggplot2`). The prototype leverages the RMarkdown language and R Notebooks to create an intuitive graphical

user interface, and can run on any operating system with a working R installation running in RStudio. Users currently enter their own data or use the provided sample datasets of synthetic calibration and test data. The module runs interactively by executing each successive code chunk, and outputs simple graphical plots of the calculated detection functions, as well as summary statistics such as effective sweep widths.

We plan to improve the usability and accessibility of this module before making it more broadly available, but its current code, written as an R notebook, is available on GitHub and archived with Zenodo (Edwards, 2024). While the R Notebook format is accessible to anyone with basic familiarity with R and Python coding environments, especially those with experience in Jupyter Notebooks, our goal is to adapt the current version of the module into a Shiny App that can be deployed in a browser. This should increase the overall accessibility of the module, making it usable by archaeologists with no prior knowledge of R, R Notebooks, or RStudio.

Expandability, Open-Source, and Open Access

We consider it desirable to add modules to accommodate other aspects of survey design and management that our current plan does not include, and would like to have users actively participate in building a database of visibility and sweep width information that would improve estimates of sweep widths and survey coverage.

Whether or not we can anticipate what future modules may be useful, it is important to construct the software in such a way that it will not be difficult to accommodate them. Further, creating the software with open-source tools such as Python and R, and hosting the code in accessible repositories such as GitHub, or by hosting interactive webapps, ensures equitable long-term access to the tools beyond the core team that initially created them (Marwick 2016, Marwick et al., 2017). Further, using accessible platforms such as GitHub facilitates central

management of the project while still encouraging community-wide co-development through “branch-and-fork” dispersed collaboration.

Conclusions

Many methods are already available to facilitate the efficient design, implementation and evaluation of archaeological surveys, but most archaeologists do not avail themselves of these tools because of the perception that they are difficult, “academic,” or of limited importance in an environment where simply following standard practices or regulations is considered sufficient. While standardization of practice has some attractions (Carver et al. 2015) — including simplicity and facilitating inter-survey comparisons — standardized surveys can also be inefficient, more costly than necessary to achieve their objectives, or vulnerable to the risk of missing significant archaeological resources that could lead to unanticipated mitigation costs or construction delays. The modules we are developing in our SPACE project will, we hope, counteract the negative perceptions and help archaeologists reap the benefits of proven methods, which include controlling the costs of surveys that still accomplish their main goal of finding the archaeological traces that we are committed to document and protect.

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Conflict of Interest Disclosure

The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest in relation to the content of the article.

Data, Scripts, Code, and Supplementary Information Availability

The R code and sample data for the sweep width module are publicly available online via Zenodo at the following persistent URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/10798638>, and can be cited using the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10798638.

Materials and Methods

The methods used to set up the calibrations and execute the calibration runs can be found on Zenodo at the following persistent URL: <https://zenodo.org/records/10801966>, and can be cited using the DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.10801965.

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